

Nickel (II) Complexes with 2-Methyl Quinoline

M. K. Misra and D. V. Ramana Rao

Two spin-free, octahedral complexes of divalent Nickel— NiL_4Cl_2 and $\text{NiL}_4(\text{CNS})_2$ where L is 2-methyl quinoline are isolated and characterised. They undergo thermal decomposition to NiLCl_2 and $\text{NiL}_2(\text{CNS})_2$ which can be converted back to tetrakis compounds on treatment with excess ligand. The infra-red spectra of thiocyanato compounds indicate the presence of terminal CNS groups.

Several divalent nickel complexes with substituted pyridines like α , β and γ -picolines were reported^{1,2} in the literature. More recently we have characterised³ the compounds having the composition NiL_nX_2 where L is 4-vinyl pyridine, n is 2 and 4 and X is Cl^- or CNS^- . In this communication, we report some more paramagnetic nickel(II) complexes obtained by reacting nickel chloride and thiocyanate with 2-methyl quinoline.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used are of A.R. grade. The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating metal and halogen or thiocyanate. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature over solid specimens using Guoy method. The conductance measurements were carried out using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The infrared absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer.

1. *Dichloro tetrakis (2-methyl quinoline) Nickel (II)*: $\text{Ni}(2\text{-meq})_4\text{Cl}_2$: To a solution of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.25 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) was added 1 ml. of 2-methyl quinoline. After shaking for 15 mins. a light green crystalline compound separated out which was filtered, washed with ethanol and petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*.

2. *Dichloro 2-methyl quinoline Nickel (II)*: $\text{Ni}(2\text{-meq})\text{Cl}_2$: The light green tetrakis (2-methyl quinoline) compound gradually loses weight on heating. When kept at 160° for 4 hr. nearly 3 moles of the ligand are lost leaving behind a yellow amorphous compound having the composition $\text{Ni}(2\text{-meq})\text{Cl}_2$.

3. *Dithiocyanato tetrakis (2-methyl quinoline) Nickel (II)*: $\text{Ni}(2\text{-meq})_4(\text{CNS})_2$: To an alcoholic solution of nickel nitrate, excess potassium thiocyanate was added. The precipitated potassium nitrate was filtered out and the filtrate containing $\text{Ni}(\text{CNS})_2$ was treated with excess 2-methyl quinoline. After shaking for 15 mins. a bluish violet crystalline

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2. S. M. Nelson and T. M. Shepherd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 3276.
3. R. N. Patel and D. V. Ramana Rao, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1967, **351**, 68.

compound separated out which was filtered, washed with ethanol and petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo*.

4. *Dithiocyanato bis-(2-methyl quinoline) Nickel (II)*: $Ni(2-meq)_2(CNS)_2$: The *bluish violet* tetrakis (2-methyl quinoline) compound starts losing weight at 120° and when kept at 140° for 10 hr., nearly 2 moles of the ligands are lost leaving behind a *light green* micro crystalline compound having the composition $Ni(2-meq)_2(CNS)_2$.

Attempts were made to prepare nitrate and perchlorate complexes of Nickel(II) with 2-methyl quinoline but no compound could be isolated and only nickel hydroxide separated out during refluxing.

TABLE I

Analysis, M.P., Conductance and Magnetic Susceptibility of Nickel(II) Complexes with 2-methyl quinoline

Compound	Colour and form	% Nickel		% Chloride/CNS		M.P. °C	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Λ_M in acetone (mhos)
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.			
1. Dichloro tetrakis (2-methyl quinoline) nickel(II).	Light green crystalline	8.8	8.8	10.1	10.1	180 <i>d</i>	3.04	13
2. Dichloro (2-methyl quinoline) nickel(II).	Yellow amorphous	21.5	22.0	26.0	26.0	>250	3.11	—
3. Dithiocyanato tetrakis (2-methyl quinoline) nickel(II).	Bluish violet crystalline	7.9	7.9	15.0	15.5	200 <i>d</i>	2.95	53
4. Dithiocyanato bis-(2-methyl quinoline) nickel(II).	Light green micro crystalline	12.3	12.4	24.7	25.2	>250	3.02	51

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analytical, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table I. All the compounds have poor solubility in alcohol, acetone and nitrobenzene. The compounds having the composition $Ni(2-meq)_4X_2$ where X is Cl^- or CNS^- have a better solubility in acetone and nitrobenzene. The low values for molar conductance, Λ_M , in acetone *viz.*, 13, 53 and 51 mhos (Table I) are indicative of their non-electrolytic nature. The slightly larger values for the thiocyanato complexes show that they undergo partial dissociation in solution. Both the tetrakis complexes are paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values of 3.04 and 2.95 B.M. indicative of the presence of 2 unpaired electrons. These compounds are therefore presumably spin-free, octahedral complexes of nickel(II) involving the use of $4s4p^34d^2$ hybrid orbitals for bonding.

The thermal decomposition studies carried out at increasing temperatures for different intervals of time are interesting. The weight loss in chloro and thiocyanato compounds is gradual and constant finally corresponding to a loss of three and two moles of the ligand respectively. The residual compounds on analysis corresponded to the composition $NiLCl_2$

and $\text{NiL}_2(\text{CNS})_2$. These compounds dissolved completely on warming with excess ligand and on cooling and stirring the tetrakis compounds are once again formed. The dithiocyanato bis(2-methyl quinoline) Nickel(II) is presumably a tetrahedral monomer since the infra-red spectrum reveals the presence of a terminal but not a bridging thiocyanate group. The compound NiLCl_2 is also expected to be a tetrahedral dimer presumably involving halogen bridges. The amorphous form and insolubility in organic solvents are in conformity with this.

The infra-red spectra of the free ligand, 2-methyl quinoline and the complexes have been recorded. Since the ligand is not free but bonded to the metal, some of the characteristic ligand absorption bands have been modified in the complexes. Chatt and Duncanson reported⁴ that terminal SCN groups absorb in the range 2100–2120 cm^{-1} , and the bridging ones in the range 2150–2180 cm^{-1} . The spectra of $\text{NiL}_4(\text{CNS})_2$ and $\text{NiL}_2(\text{CNS})_2$ reveal sharp bands at 2075 cm^{-1} and 2100 cm^{-1} respectively indicating the presence of only terminal thiocyanate groups. The presence of halogen bridges could not be indicated due to the limitation of the range of the instrument.

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Department of Chemistry,
Regional Engineering College,
Rourkela-8 (Orissa).

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